

DELIVERABLE D6.4

Report on the preparation methodology
of n- and p-type silicides using Si-kerf and their properties

Work Package No - Title	WP6 - From technological value to the market - high-end applications
Work Package Leader (partner)	SINTEF
Author (partner):	Theodora Kyratsi
Other authors:	Panagiotis Mangelis (UCY)
Date released by WP leader	01.12.2023
Date released by Coordinator	22.12.2023

Dissemination Level	
PU: Public	x
CO: Confidential, only for members for the consortium	

Deliverable type	
R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DIS: Websites, patents, filing, press and media actions, videos, etc	
OTHER: Software, technical diagram	
ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	

Revision:			
Version	Date	Changed	Comments
1.0	22.12.2023		Final

CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	4
2	RAW MATERIALS: RECYCLABLE SILICON KERF	4
3	FABRICATION OF N-TYPE SILICIDE TE MATERIALS	4
4	FABRICATION OF P-TYPE SILICIDE TE MATERIALS.....	5
5	CONCLUSIONS	7

1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to give an overview of the current status of Task 6.4. Two types of thermoelectric (TE) legs are required for the development of the TE Module (TEM). The up-to-date results are presented separately for the n- and p-type materials using recycled silicon kerf. Kerf options, methodology of materials synthesis and processing, material characterization data as well as data of TE properties and efficiency of developed materials are presented here.

2 RAW MATERIALS: RECYCLABLE SILICON KERF

The silicon kerf has been supplied and processed by ReSiTec AS. Two different recycled purified silicon materials have been developed in powder form from the kerf.

- RST 1-2
- RST ODIN-0821

The elemental analysis of two developed Si powders shows slight amounts of impurities such as Ca, Al, Fe and Ni in the scale of few hundreds ppm. Powder XRD confirms the desired single phase of Si without secondary phases.

3 FABRICATION OF N-TYPE SILICIDE TE MATERIALS

Bi doped $Mg_2(Si, Sn)$ TE materials were synthesized using both, pure Si and Si-kerf, by two different methods:

- Mechanical Alloying (MA) and
- Solid State Reaction (SSR).

Subsequently, hot press (HP) sintering was carried out to consolidate the developed powders into high-density pellets/legs.

3.1 Mechanical Alloying Synthesis

For the MA synthesis, initial reactant elements (Mg, Si, Sn, Bi) were mixed in appropriate ratios under Ar atmosphere and then ball milled in a Fritsch planetary mill, under Ar atmosphere. Hot pressing followed at high temperature and pressure to consolidate the powder into high density pellets. The Si kerf-based materials were studied in terms of their structure, morphology as well as thermoelectric performance and they were compared with the same composition developed by using pure polycrystalline Si-5N from Alfa Aesar. The MA method steps are shown in the following flow chart:

Powder XRD confirms the desired silicide phase. MgO is also identified in the two kerf-based compounds made of the two kerfs. TE characterization of fabricated pellets/legs followed in the temperature range 25 – 500 °C. TE property measurements of developed materials by using the two types of Si kerfs demonstrate promising TE performance with efficiencies around 1 especially for the RST ODIN-0821 kerf.

3.2 Solid State Reaction Synthesis

For the SSR method, the steps are shown in the following flow chart:

Powder XRD patterns of the developed materials confirm the desired silicide phase formation. Small amounts of MgO are detected in the two kerf-based materials.

Seebeck coefficient and electrical conductivity measurements of developed materials were carried out in order to determine their TE Power Factor (PF). It is notable that the PF of the materials prepared by the two kerfs reach relatively good values ($> 20 \mu\text{W cm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$), demonstrating a quite promising performance for the fabrication of TE modules.

4 FABRICATION OF P-TYPE SILICIDE TE MATERIALS

The synthesis of p-type silicides were focused on two different systems:

- p-type $\text{Mg}_2(\text{Si},\text{Sn})$ system using Li as dopant
- p-type Higher Manganese Silicide (HMS) system.

P-type $\text{Mg}_2(\text{Si},\text{Sn})$ system:

Li-doped $\text{Mg}_2(\text{Si},\text{Sn})$ materials were synthesized using the two types of recycled kerf via MA method. Subsequently, HP sintering was carried out to consolidate the developed powders into high-density

pellets/legs. XRD of the selected members confirm that the synthesis of Li-doped silicides using RST1-2 and RST ODIN-0821 was successful in terms of materials purity. XRD shows the single-phase of typical silicide structure without any impurities. Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity were carried out as a function of temperature for the developed materials. The Seebeck coefficient presents *p*-type behavior, confirming that the synthesis was successful in terms of charge carriers in the transport properties. The TE figure-of-merit of developed materials was determined demonstrating quite promising values for the case of RST 1-2, although lower than those of *n*-type. The main advantage of using this material as the *p*-type leg for the TE modules is the fact that both, *p*- and *n*-type legs, will have very similar mechanical features, therefore, better TEM development and operation.

P-type Higher Manganese Silicide (HMS)

For the HMS system, compositions of MnSi_δ (δ from 1.71 to 1.77) were studied using commercially available silicon as well as the two types of Si kerf. The synthesis was attempted following two methods:

- Mechanical alloying followed by hot press sintering
- Arc melting followed by short ball milling and hot press sintering

Mechanical alloying method

Compositions of MnSi_δ (δ from 1.71 to 1.77) were studied using commercially available silicon as well as the two types of Si kerf. Mn and Si elements were weighed in a glovebox under Ar atmosphere according to the desired stoichiometry and the mixtures were loaded into a tungsten carbide vial. The obtained powders were loaded in a cylindrical graphite die and hot-pressed under an axial pressure. XRD results show that after few hours of milling, the desired HMS phase was developed but a secondary MnSi phase is also detected.

The TE characterization of materials developed by the two types of Si kerf was carried out, showing that the RST 1-2 demonstrates a promising TE performance. More work on the synthesis conditions to eliminate the secondary phase is in progress and further studies are going to be carried out to enlighten the TE properties of investigated materials the following period.

Arc melting method

Silicon powder (Si-5N, RST ODIN-0821, RST 1-2) and manganese powder (99.5%) were weighed at appropriate ratios of MnSi_δ and then were cold pressed into pellets. The pressed pellets were

melted in an arc-melting furnace under argon atmosphere. The samples were ball milled for 30 min for obtaining fine powder. The resulted powders were loaded in a cylindrical graphite die and hot-pressed under argon atmosphere.

The Arc Melting method produced single-phase compounds for the Si kerf materials. Comparing the two synthesis methods, arc melting presents better results for the two kerf cases in terms of materials purity. From the point of view of TE properties, the RST ODIN-0821-based material exhibits a promising PF.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The materials studied for both, n- and p-type, were based on $Mg_2(Si,Sn)$ system. Moreover, higher manganese silicides were also studied as an alternative p-type system, since p-type $Mg_2(Si,Sn)$ was not performing as good as the n-type. In all cases the materials were prepared using commercially available Si with purity 5N as well as Si kerf provided by ReSiTeC (RST-ODIN-821 and RST1-2). The best compositions in terms of TE properties for each system are included in this report.

n-type Si-rich $Mg_2(Si,Sn)$ TE materials prepared using Si kerfs showed very good results in terms of TE properties. Among the two different types of kerf, RST-ODIN-0821 gave higher TE efficiency. Regarding the synthesis techniques, the materials had very good TE properties in both cases, prepared by mechanical alloying as well as by solid state reaction.

On the other hand, p-type materials presented lower PF and ZT values. Although these values are considerably lower than those of n-type, they are still promising for the development of TEMs. Between the two p-type systems, Li-doped $Mg_2(Si,Sn)$ showed higher ZT, but lower power factor than the HMS case.